

THE ROLE OF CHEMISTRY IN THE TRAINING OF ENGINEERING STAFF*Jabbarova N.**Candidate of Chemical Sciences, Associate Professor,**Maharramova L.**Candidate of Chemical Sciences, Associate Professor**Department of Chemistry and Technology of Inorganic Substances,**Faculty of Chemical Technology,**Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University, Baku.***Abstract**

The article examines the role and importance of chemical disciplines in higher educational institutions for the training of engineering personnel in the Republic of Azerbaijan. Information is provided on the development of the chemical industry - plants for the production of metals, alloys, fertilizers, etc. The work of young scientists carried out at the University is noted

Keywords: chemical disciplines, industry, engineering personnel, young scientists, Azerbaijan.

Throughout the existence of Mankind, chemistry has served in its practical activities.

The development of such industries as metallurgy, mechanical engineering, transport, production of building materials, electronics, light food industries, household spheres and many other areas is associated with chemistry.

Water is the most amazing substance - the basis of life on Earth. Every year, more than 450 billion cubic meters of household and industrial waste are dumped into rivers around the world. The task of chemistry is to purify contaminated fresh water and desalinate salt water [1-3].

A huge amount of chemical weapons is accumulating all over the world, which even only during storage are a "time bomb". The development of methods for the disposal of chemical weapons and used materials is also the task of chemistry.

Chemistry plays a major role in the development of the pharmaceutical industry, as well as in the search for new materials that can replace living tissue.

New food products, cosmetics, etc. – all this cannot exist without chemistry.

Unfortunately, in the last decade, there has been a decline in the level of chemistry education in secondary schools in Azerbaijan, and an objective attitude has formed towards this subject as complex and unclaimed in further professional activity. Therefore, complications often arise when studying this discipline at a university. The problem is further aggravated by the fact that with the destruction of the Soviet education system, the chemistry course in universities was cut by in half or even more, i.e. a capacious deep course of higher education had to be cut back and completed at a rapid pace, which, of course, cannot but affect the learning outcomes.

But modern society needs educated youth who should be able to implement their own developments in various fields of science, technology, and production in their professional activities.

Such successful activity is possible only on the basis of a harmonious understanding of the world, the environment, and a conscious search for one's own place in everyday life. Therefore, knowledge of fundamental scientific and natural sciences, including chemistry, becomes a necessary basis for ensuring fruitful productive

professional activity of university graduates and the ability to solve problems and possible future global problems.

Taking into account many years of experience in training engineering personnel and modern requirements in the preparation of bachelors of general technical fields in light of the requirements of the Bologna education system, the scientific and pedagogical staff of the Azerbaijan State Oil and Industry University consistently works on the problem of forming a high-quality system of students' knowledge in fundamental disciplines (chemistry, mathematics, physics). Mastering knowledge of the main natural sciences in the first years of study becomes the key to forming a fundamental worldview of the nature of objects and the surrounding world around us in students. It is the expansion and improvement of fundamental training that allows us to develop specialists capable of thinking outside the box, analyzing, systematizing and generalizing the information received, and solving real technical problems [4-7].

The Department of Chemistry and Technology of Inorganic Substances has been training masters in the specialty of inorganic substance technology and processing of solid household and industrial waste for several years. Scientific research is conducted under the supervision of the department's teachers, the results of which are published in various scientific journals. Republican and international conferences with the participation of young scientists are held annually [8-13].

A high level of engineering work in solving technological problems can be based on a deep understanding of the chemical laws of processes that are basic in the creation of new technological industries. This requires a significant expansion of pedagogical methods.

The widespread use of animation, chemical modeling via a computer makes learning more visual, understandable and memorable. The use of different types of educational activities - creating presentations, performing laboratory work in a virtual laboratory, testing, etc. - allows students to independently obtain the necessary information, think, reason, analyze, and draw conclusions.

An important advantage of using complex technologies in chemistry laboratory classes is the ability to

demonstrate chemical experiments that are difficult to carry out in the laboratory.

The use of "virtual excursions" significantly broadens the horizons of students and facilitates their understanding of the features of production processes.

Ultimately, the knowledge gained during the training allows students to interpret technical, natural science, and humanitarian problems of our time in the context of the relationship between geology, chemistry, ecology, and the study of environmental pollution problems, etc.

Each specialist, whether an instrument engineer, a thermal power engineer, an oilman, or a specialist in the field of biomedical engineering or microelectronics, must, at least, have a sufficient understanding of those "chemical components" of their activities that contribute to the intensification and improvement of work results.

For example, significant qualitative changes in the field of microelectronics can only be realized with the use of new semiconductor materials that can be developed using nanotechnology. Metallic and metal-ceramic materials can be modified with additives of carbides and nitrides, which are characterized by unique performance properties, in particular high resistance to corrosion and wear in various temperature conditions.

In the energy sector, significant achievements are possible due to a deep understanding of the chemical properties of fuel combustion processes, the principles of controlling (managing) the kinetic properties of processes using substances that stabilize combustion processes, prevent scale formation in boilers and reduce wear of parts.

But the allocation of an insignificant amount of credits for the study of a much-needed fundamental discipline as chemistry, or its complete absence as a subject in the curricula of some technical areas of bachelor's degree course does not guarantee the formation of a modern, well-rounded specialist.

It is necessary to deepen and improve the chemical training of bachelors of higher education institutions not only to broaden the worldview of the future specialist, but also to successfully complete engineering developments and solve technological problems.

Currently, our republic has a difficult situation on the labor market. No one can say exactly what kind of specialists and how many need to be trained for the next 5-10 years. There is no understanding of what which specialists are required.

Today, the labor market needs specialists with interdisciplinary knowledge, who can quickly retrain, make effective decisions in dynamically changing conditions.

In Azerbaijan, over the past 20-25 years, there has been a significant growth of industrial facilities, especially those related to the chemical industry. Since 2013, an industrial chemical park (200 hectares) has been launched in Sumgait (Azerbaijan), including 13 operating facilities (including a copper processing plant, a plant for the production of copper wires of various cross-sections, a plant for the production of plastic windows and doors of the Assorep company, etc.), an aluminum rolling plant, a ferroalloy plant, etc.

The Azersun industrial park includes a paper and cardboard plant, a factory for the production of vegetable oils and other products. The oil company SOCAR launched the Methanol plant, a urea carbamide plant, and the Polimer plant. In Balakhani, there is an industrial park with two plants for sorting and recycling household waste (as part of the "clean city" project) [14].

An industrial park has been launched in the city of Mingachevir (since 2016), and food processing plants and factories operate in the regions of the Republic. And the list goes on and on...

Training a new generation of engineers who are capable of ensuring the competitiveness of products both in the national commodity market and in the global world market is an urgent task for engineering universities.

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